

Managerial Competence of School Principals in Implementing Learning After the Covid-19 Pandemic in Elementary Schools

Dwi Hardaningtyas¹, Rudy Handoko², Bambang Kusbandrijo³

¹Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik, Universitas Wijaya Putra Surabaya

^{2,3}Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik, Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya

[¹dwiwardaningtyas@uwp.ac.id](mailto:dwiwardaningtyas@uwp.ac.id), [²rudyhandoko62@yahoo.com](mailto:rudyhandoko62@yahoo.com), [³b_kusbandrijo@untag-sby.ac.id](mailto:b_kusbandrijo@untag-sby.ac.id)

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to describe, analyze and evaluate the role of principal managerial competence in supporting the implementation of learning after the Covid-19 pandemic in elementary schools. The principal has a role as a manager in determining the school management process by carrying out management functions consisting of planning, organizing, implementing and supervising. This research is a qualitative descriptive research. Data collection was obtained from various sources and relevant backgrounds (documents, books, magazines, news) with a systematic literature review technique. The criteria for the selected articles and news were discussions about the concept of managerial competence of school principals, the positive and negative impacts of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as learning after the Covid-19 pandemic in elementary schools. The result of this study is the identification of the appropriate managerial competence of the principal and is needed in the implementation of learning after the Covid-19 pandemic in elementary schools.

Keywords: *principals; principal managerial competence; learning; learning strategy*

A. Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic is a phenomenon that has brought many changes to various activities in human life in the world, including in Indonesia. Various health strategies and protocols have been used to break the chain of transmission of COVID-19 (Sarah Amalyah, 2021). In the education sector, the Minister of Education and Culture of Indonesia issued Circular No. 4 of 2020 concerning the Implementation of Education Policies in the Emergency Period of the Spread of Covid-19, that each education unit conducts learning through a learning from home system (BDR) which aims to protect and prevent adverse effects from the transmission of Covid-19 in the educational environment (Kemendikbud, 2020). In addition, this distance learning aims to keep learning going and can provide a meaningful learning experience for each student.

This change from face-to-face learning to distance learning requires adaptation in its implementation. The obstacle in distance learning according to Rigianti (2020) is that it is not supported by adequate availability of gadgets and internet networks, so that management, assessment is not optimal and implementation has minimal supervision. According to Utami

(2020) online learning uses telecommunications media such as smartphones or laptops, so it is an extra demand for schools, because both the school and students are not familiar with this system. The problem that arises at the level of understanding of students is that students do not understand the material provided by the teacher. Khaerudin (2020) explains that parents are worried about their children's boredom with the assignments given by the teacher. The teacher readiness factor in online learning also has an effect on student learning outcomes. Not all teachers have adequate skills in information technology. This will certainly affect the academic achievement of students (Oktaviani, Abidin, Yuanita, & Cahyadi, 2021).

Entering the post-pandemic Covid-19 period, the implementation of learning in schools has returned to normal, namely through face-to-face meetings with an adjusted schedule. The Director of Elementary Schools of the Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture, Sri Wahyuningsih stated that we all need strategies in the transition to the post-pandemic era. (Hendriyanto, 2021). The first thing that needs to be done is to plan a management strategy in the field of education. Likewise with the education system, there needs to be reform so that education after the corona outbreak can be resolved (Winandi, 2020). In this case the role of the Principal in the Education unit is very necessary. According to Wahyudi (2012) the principal is a leader, driving force and policy maker in an educational institution. Rusdiana (2016) explains that a leader is someone who has the ability to move, direct, give orders, provide solutions while influencing the mindset of each subordinate in order to achieve the set goals. This ability is very much needed in dealing with situations that occur in an educational institution in the conditions of the co-19 pandemic (Oktaviani, Abidin, Yuanita, & Cahyadi, 2021).

In carrying out its function as a manager, the Principal determines the school management process by carrying out management functions consisting of planning, organizing, implementing and supervising. The competencies needed in this case are managerial competencies. Managerial competence is the principal's ability to organize and develop school resources to create an effective and efficient learning environment. Principals are required to have skills in developing the human resources available in their schools, so that they can truly be empowered and contribute to achieving educational goals in schools. (Ismuha, Khairudin, & AR, 2016). The principal must be able to carry out school management and his performance must be seen in carrying out this managerial field (Tanjung, Hanafiah, Arifudin, & Mulyadi, 2021).

One thing to realize is that the quality of education tends to decline. Improving the quality of education in the post-Covid-19 pandemic is very important (Winandi, 2020). This has

attracted the attention of researchers to understand in depth the role of school principals' managerial competencies in supporting the implementation of post-Covid-19 pandemic learning in elementary schools.

Learning During the Covid-19 Pandemic

1. Nur, Ika and Rita's research (2021) aims to analyze problems in the online or distance learning process at the elementary school level during the Covid-19 pandemic. The subjects were class teachers, subject teachers and students in elementary schools in the Kalijambe sub-district, Sragen, totaling 30 people. The results of observations and interviews show that 80% of informants experience problems in online learning, especially in terms of learning support facilities, understanding of technology, low enthusiasm for learning, achievement of learning objectives that are not optimal. The online learning process requires a minimal Android communication tool and requires an internet network with connectivity, accessibility and flexibility. Many students don't have their own android, so they use their parent's android to study, while parents of students work and have limited time to access lessons provided by teachers online. The Ministry of Education and Culture provides internet quota assistance, but many students who live in villages find it very difficult to get a stable internet network and require them to walk to a certain place to get a network. This reduces their enthusiasm for learning(Nur Harizah Zain, 2021).
2. Study Noorfazly, et al (2021) aims to present information regarding the perspective of elementary school teachers regarding the implementation of online learning. An open questionnaire was given online to 88 elementary school teachers in Indonesia who teach with an online learning system. This study develops a learning process model from Gage & Berliner (1992) which focuses on variables that teachers must consider when designing, executing and evaluating. The results that were informed in this study were that 84% of teachers responded that the implementation of online learning was felt to be less effective in achieving learning objectives. The basis for assessing the ineffectiveness of online learning is because at the design stage, lack of preparation for learning, limited facilities (gadgets, quotas, networks), lack of mastery of IT; at the execute stage, there are network disturbances, limited delivery of material, lack of involvement of students and parents, assignments are done by parents, teachers find it difficult to arrange teaching and learning time; evaluate stage, learning objectives are not achieved, learning outcomes are doubtful, difficulty assessing affective and psychomotor aspects. Efforts made by the teacher in overcoming online learning at the design stage, the teacher prepares lesson plans and implements teaching and learning according to conditions, is more creative in selecting

and using teaching methods/materials, prepares adequate tools and further improves self-ability; at the execute stage, the teacher monitors student progress and assignments, presents interesting material, adjusts learning rules that are more flexible, repeats material, if necessary can home visit, establishes good communication between fellow teachers, parents and students regarding the learning process; at the evaluate stage, the teacher can make an evaluation method that is appropriate to the conditions, using video conferencing to conduct the exam. These efforts can be an alternative that can be done to increase the effectiveness of implementing online learning. Teachers and parents are important points in supporting the effectiveness of the online learning process for students at the elementary level.(Oktaviani, Abidin, Yuanita, & Cahyadi, 2021)

Learning Post Pandemic Covid-19

1. In Johar and Widya's research (2022) it was stated that learning conducted from home had an impact on students, students became less sociable, students experienced verbal violence, students lacked discipline in learning at home, learning facilities were inadequate and students' learning objectives were not achieved. Online learning is even considered not to make a positive contribution to the affective development of students, only creative characters develop. This study aims to describe full face-to-face learning after the pandemic at Salebu 03 Public Elementary School, Majenang District, Cilacap Regency. This school has implemented face-to-face learning since the beginning of the 2022-2023 school year. After conducting interviews with the Principal, grade 6 teachers and grade 2 teachers, representatives of parents and students, It is known that the transition from online learning to face-to-face learning requires an adaptation process. The new habit that accompanies this learning process is that students must adapt (1) get up early, because they have to go to school early; (2) studying quietly and focusing in class with the guidance of the teacher, doing assignments independently according to one's own abilities and knowledge without the help of parents; (3) socializing with friends and teachers at school; (4) keep adapting to implementing health protocols (diligently maintaining cleanliness, washing hands and wearing masks). (2) studying quietly and focusing in class with the guidance of the teacher, doing assignments independently according to one's own abilities and knowledge without the help of parents; (3) socializing with friends and teachers at school; (4) keep adapting to implementing health protocols (diligently maintaining cleanliness, washing hands and wearing masks). (2) studying quietly and focusing in class with the guidance of the teacher, doing assignments independently according to one's own abilities and knowledge without the help of parents; (3) socializing with friends and

teachers at school; (4) keep adapting to implementing health protocols (diligently maintaining cleanliness, washing hands and wearing masks).

The implementation of face-to-face learning after the covid-19 pandemic also has various challenges: (1) the learning system must consider high safety and effectiveness, study hours are not too long but can convey material that is dense and easily understood by students, and still directs students to become more creative, innovative, independent, and productive; (2) teachers must be creative to find learning strategies or methods that can quickly make students adapt to face-to-face learning at school.

The obstacles in the online learning process are mainly in the formation of the character of students who cannot be replaced by technology. The ineffectiveness of character education during a pandemic needs to be corrected after the pandemic, especially in schools, because schools are students' second home. Teachers have a big responsibility in producing generations with character, culture and morality. The role of the teacher in building the character of post-covid-19 students includes exemplary, habituation, advice, stories/stories, as well as the reward and punishment method. An example of character planting activities is the daily picket. This activity instills the character of discipline, responsibility and cooperation through habituation which is carried out every week by students

The positive impact of the Covid-19 pandemic is increasing the use of technology in the implementation of education. Post-pandemic Face-to-Face Learning (PTM) should not even set back progress in understanding technology that has been achieved. Technology can be used as a support or as a variation of media during post-pandemic face-to-face learning so that learning is more efficient, for example when a student is unable to attend school he can still learn through technological assistance (blogs, Google Classroom, Video/Youtube etc.) so that these students do not miss the material presented by the teacher in class.(Johar Alimuddin, 2022)

2. Research conducted by Dewi and Agung (2022) aims to describe the Merdeka Curriculum as a form of independent learning in elementary schools regarding the profile of Pancasila students, the structure of the Merdeka Curriculum in elementary schools, and the teaching tools used. In this study, Dewi and Agung explained the curriculum that was in effect in Indonesia during the Covid-19 pandemic until entering 2022 in the context of recovering learning from 2022 to 2024 due to the pandemic.

At the time of the Covid-19 pandemic, the curriculum used was the 2013 curriculum. Citing what was conveyed by Anwar (2014) that the implementation of K-13 focuses on

phenomena that occur in the surrounding environment such as natural, social, artistic and cultural phenomena through observing, asking, try, reason and communicate so that students are more creative, innovative and productive and ready to face problems. During a pandemic, learning activities were carried out online with a learning intensity of approximately 2-3 hours per day per day. The impact of this learning is the emergence of parental anxiety because of limitations in children's learning capacity, lack of teacher guidance and really expect parents to be full companions of children's learning, Furthermore, there are regulations to anticipate the widening impact that occurs in learning during the pandemic on learning loss and learning gaps. This policy is contained in the Decree of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 719/P/2020 concerning Guidelines for Implementing Curriculum in Education Units Under Special Conditions (2020). In this emergency curriculum, teachers and students can focus on essential competencies and prerequisite competencies for continuing learning at the next level. Teachers are encouraged to carry out continuous diagnostic assessments to examine students' cognitive and non-cognitive states as a result of learning from home or distance learning. Through this diagnostic assessment, teachers can provide learning that is appropriate to the conditions and needs of students. After running for almost one school year, the Ministry of Education and Culture evaluated the implementation of the emergency curriculum and obtained evaluation results that students using the emergency curriculum got better assessment results than those using the curriculum. 2013 in full. implementing an emergency curriculum can significantly reduce learning-loss during the pandemic both for literacy and numeracy achievements (Anggraena et al., in Dewi 2022: 7175). The Ministry of Education and Culture evaluated the implementation of the emergency curriculum and obtained evaluation results that students who used the emergency curriculum got better assessment results than those who used the 2013 curriculum in full. implementing an emergency curriculum can significantly reduce learning-loss during the pandemic both for literacy and numeracy achievements (Anggraena et al., in Dewi 2022: 7175). The Ministry of Education and Culture evaluated the implementation of the emergency curriculum and obtained evaluation results that students who used the emergency curriculum got better assessment results than those who used the 2013 curriculum in full. implementing an emergency curriculum can significantly reduce learning-loss during the pandemic both for literacy and numeracy achievements (Anggraena et al., in Dewi 2022: 7175).

The Independent Curriculum set by Nadiem Makarim begins with four Free Learning policies presented by the Ministry of Education and Culture, (2021a) including (1) In 2020, replace the National Standardized School Examination (USBN) with a test or assessment organized by the school with competency assessment students can be done in a variety of more comprehensive forms that give freedom to teachers and schools to assess student learning outcomes. (2) In 2021, the National Examination will change to a Minimum Competency Assessment (AKM) and a Character Survey that focuses on literacy, numeracy and character abilities as an effort to encourage teachers and schools to improve the quality of learning that refers to international good practice assessments such as PISA and TIMSS. (3) Simplification in the preparation of Learning Implementation Plans (RPP), which originally consisted of 13 components to become 3 core components covering learning objectives, learning activities and assessments. This is intended so that teachers have more time to prepare and evaluate learning in addition to effectiveness and efficiency. (4) policies in New Student Admissions that are more flexible so as to be able to support inequality in terms of access and quality in the regions.

The Independent Curriculum is an option for schools that are ready to implement it in the context of recovering learning from 2022 to 2024 due to the pandemic. The implementation of this curriculum refers to the Decree of the Minister of Education, Culture, Research and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia Number 56/M/2022 concerning Guidelines for Implementing Curriculum in the Context of Recovery Learning Development & Learning (2022). The advantages of the Independent Curriculum explained by the Ministry of Education and Culture (2021b) focus on essential material and develop student competence in its phases so that students can learn more deeply, meaningfully and have fun, not in a hurry. Learning is far more relevant and interactive through project activities providing wider opportunities for students to actively explore actual issues such as environmental, health,

In this study, Dewi classified the dimensions and elements of the Pancasila Student Profile based on Decree Number 009/H/KR/2022 from the Head of the Curriculum Standards and Education Assessment Agency. Planting student character education with a Pancasila student profile, consisting of 6 dimensions, namely:

1. Having faith, fearing God Almighty and having noble character
Elements: Religious morals, personal morals, morals to humans, morals to nature, national morals
2. Global Diversity

Elements: Recognizing and appreciating culture, Communication and interaction between cultures, Reflection and responsibility for the experience of diversity, Social justice

3. Mutual cooperation

Elements : Collaboration, Caring, Sharing

4. Independent

Elements: Understanding yourself and the situation, Self-regulation

5. Critical Reasoning

Elements: Obtaining and processing information and ideas, Analyzing and evaluating reasoning, Reflecting and evaluating their own thoughts

6. Creative

Elements: Produce original ideas, Produce original works and actions, Have the flexibility of thinking in finding alternative solutions to problems

(Dewi Rahmadayanti, 2022)

Principal Managerial Competence

1. Tanjung, Hanafiah, Arifudin and Mulyadi (2021) conducted a literature study which aimed to find out the planning, implementation, evaluation and solutions of school principals in improving the performance of elementary school teachers. In this study, the existence of an effective principal is the main thing. The success or failure of achieving school goals is influenced by the ability of the principal in carrying out management functions (planning, organizing, implementing, supervising). As a manager, the principal determines the school management process. The problems that arise in the implementation of the planning function are (1) the Principal prepares the same activity plan as in previous years; (2) in making school plans not through meetings involving educators and education staff so that the plans are not in accordance with the needs of teachers and schools; (3) Planning is only to fulfill administrative requirements; (4) The implementation of existing plans is not carried out in a serious and professional manner. In carrying out the organizing function, the problems that arise are that the Principal (1) has not adapted the abilities of each teacher to the functions and responsibilities; (2) not optimal in utilizing human resources; (3) reluctant to arrange senior teachers regarding their responsibilities, where senior teachers find it difficult to keep up with system changes and learning processes that use computer technology media, causing their contribution to the implementation of education to be less than optimal. Whereas in the function of monitoring and controlling

the problems faced are that the Principal has not carried out routine supervision of his subordinates, supervision is only carried out during teacher performance assessments. The results and discussion in this study are in the form of strategies for overcoming problems in the implementation of the principal's managerial functions. In terms of planning, the school principal (1) prepares a plan based on an analysis of school needs in accordance with the school's vision and mission; (2) the process of recruiting new teachers according to the required competencies; (3) make an annual school work plan (RKTS) which concerns 8 education standards; (4) provide employee performance target criteria (SKP) at the beginning of the year as an assessment of teacher performance; (5) making supervision plans, administrative inspection plans, making schedules for teacher participation in technical training, seminars, KKG, and giving permission to continue education for teachers who are not yet linear. In the implementation function, school principals improve teacher performance by involving teachers in scientific forums (workshops, seminars), providing teacher support facilities in the learning process, and involving teachers in the teacher certification program. As for the evaluation function, its implementation is during the learning process and at the end of the learning year in the context of program achievement. (Tanjung, Hanafiah, Arifudin, & Mulyadi, 2021)

B. Methods

This research uses a literature study approach which means data collection techniques by examining books, literature, notes, and various reports related to the problem to be solved (Nazir, 2003). The criteria for selected articles and news are articles that discuss the positive and negative impacts of online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic, as well as post-Covid-19 pandemic learning and the managerial competence of school principals

C. Results and Discussion

For some people, the Covid-19 pandemic may be considered to have passed, but its impact can still be felt today. The impact that was most felt in the field of education was when the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Indonesia issued a Policy for Implementation of Education in Emergency Situations of the Spread of Corona Virus Disease (Covid-19). This policy regulates changes in the learning process, where initially learning was carried out face-to-face and changed to learning from home (BDR) with the help of telecommunication media (smartphones, laptops, internet). The Directorate of Elementary Schools of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia has made efforts to strengthen and expand

digitalization of schools, including in the 3T area, but there are internet network constraints with connectivity, accessibility and flexibility ((Nur Harizah Zain, 2021)be one of the reasons for the achievement of learning objectives that are not optimal. From the teacher's point of view, at first not all teachers had sufficient skills in information technology(Oktaviani, Abidin, Yuanita, & Cahyadi, 2021). The online learning process also has an impact on the lack of character formation of students, because students are less disciplined in learning, assignments are often done by parents. On the other hand, the Covid-19 pandemic has had a positive impact on the development of information technology skills for teachers and students.

With regard to character education, the Merdeka Curriculum is an option for schools that are ready to carry out learning recovery from 2022 to 2024 due to the pandemic. In the 2022/2023 school year, several schools in Indonesia at the elementary school level have started using the independent curriculum. The Directorate of Elementary Schools of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia also provides optimization of PHBS, scale-up of driving schools and strengthening of Pancasila Student Profiles through several learning modes (online, offline, project based learning).

Quality is an important part of education (Sri Suhandiah, 2022), effective school principals are a very important factor in facing challenges in the post-pandemic period Covid-19. The principal as a manager has a role in determining the process of managing school management. The success or failure of school goals can be influenced by the ability of the school principal to carry out management functions, which consist of planning, organizing, implementing, and supervising. In accordance with the Decree of the Minister of National Education regarding managerial competence, one of which is that the Principal must be able to carry out school management, and his performance must be seen in carrying out this managerial field (Tanjung, 2020).

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